

GEOMETRICALLY NON-LINEAR FINITE ELEMENT MODELING OF MICROELECTROMECHANICAL STRUCTURES SUBJECTED TO ELECTROSTATIC LOADING

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Abstract: A general and consistent hybrid non-linear finite element/boundary element method is developed for the purpose of modeling the deformations in an elastic structure under the action of electrostatic forces. Problems of this type occur frequently in the analysis and design of microelectromechanical systems (MEMS) in which electrostatic actuation is used. Numerous MEMS structures, such as spatial light modulators, deformable micromirrors, and microvalves, have been developed in recent years which use an electrostatic actuation scheme. Because of the highly non-linear nature of the electro-elastic behavior of these systems, the process of designing such structures requires a general and powerful numerical technique. An incremental non-linear finite element method is formulated which uses a boundary element solution at each load step to update the electrostatic force on the body and the simple example of a deformable diaphragm is investigated.

Introduction

A general and rigorous non-linear finite element/boundary element method is developed for the purpose of modeling the deformations in an elastic structure under the action of electrostatic forces. Problems of this type occur frequently in the analysis and design of microelectromechanical systems (MEMS) in which electrostatic actuation is used. To solve such problems, an incremental non-linear finite element method [3] is formulated which uses a boundary element solution at each load step to update the electrostatic force on the body. A small strain large deflection assumption is used in the implementation of the method. The basic equations are derived and an example problem involving the nonlinear deflection of a silicon diaphragm under the action of electrostatic forces is studied.

Development of The Incremental Non-Linear Elastic Finite Element Equations

The deformation of a continuous medium initially

occupying a volume V_0 with bounding surface S_0 , with coordinates X_i in the reference configuration, can be described by the relation

$$x_i = X_i + u_i, \quad (1)$$

where x_i represents the coordinates of the deformed configuration with u_i denoting the displacement components. The principle of virtual work in terms of the Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensors in the reference configuration can be stated as [1]

$$\int_{S_0} t_j^0 \delta x_j dS_0 = \frac{1}{2} \int_{V_0} \tilde{T}_{IJ} \delta C_{IJ} dV_0, \quad (2)$$

where C_{IJ} is the Green deformation tensor, t_i^0 is the traction on the deformed surface dS per unit undeformed area dS_0 , and \tilde{T}_{IJ} represents the second Piola-Kirchhoff stress. These quantities are given explicitly as

$$C_{IJ} = \frac{\partial x_k}{\partial X_I} \frac{\partial x_k}{\partial X_J}, \quad t_i^0 = \tau_{ij} J \frac{\partial X_L}{\partial x_j} N_L, \quad \text{and} \quad \tilde{T}_{IJ} = J \frac{\partial X_I}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial X_J}{\partial x_l} \tau_{kl} \quad (3)$$

In equations 3 J denotes the jacobian of the deformation and τ_{ij} is the ordinary stress tensor. The development of the finite element equations begins by interpolating the displacements using an appropriately chosen set of shape functions, N^p , as

$$u_i = N^p \bar{u}_i^p \quad \text{and} \quad \delta u_i = N^p \delta \bar{u}_i^p, \quad (4)$$

where \bar{u}_i^p represents the i^{th} component of the displacement of the p^{th} node. In equation 4 the repeated superscripts are intended to imply a sum over nodes within an element or an entire mesh, depending upon context. This notation will be employed throughout to save space. The shape functions N^p may take on several forms and will not be explicitly defined here. The reader is referred to

[4] and [5] for these and other omitted finite element definitions. Using equation 4 in the variational statement gives

$$\int_{S_0} \tau_k^{0NP} dS_0 \delta u_k^p = \int_{V_0} \tilde{T}_{IJ} \left[\frac{\partial NP}{\partial X_J} \delta_{IK} + \frac{\partial N^q \partial NP}{\partial X_I \partial X_J} \bar{u}_k^q \right] dV_0 \delta u_k^p \quad (5)$$

For arbitrary variations, δu_k^p , the following equation results:

$$f_k^p = \int_{V_0} \tilde{T}_{IJ} \left[\frac{\partial NP}{\partial X_J} \delta_{IK} + \frac{\partial N^q \partial NP}{\partial X_I \partial X_J} \bar{u}_k^q \right] dV_0. \quad (6)$$

For a small linear increment of displacement, $\Delta \bar{u}_L^r$, equation 6 is written in incremental form as

$$\Delta f_k^p = \int_{V_0} \Delta \tilde{T}_{IJ} \left[\frac{\partial NP}{\partial X_J} \delta_{IK} + \frac{\partial N^q \partial NP}{\partial X_I \partial X_J} \bar{u}_k^q \right] dV_0 + \int_{V_0} \tilde{T}_{IJ} \frac{\partial N^q \partial NP}{\partial X_I \partial X_J} \Delta \bar{u}_k^q dV_0 \quad (7)$$

The material under consideration is assumed to follow a linear elastic constitutive law which allows the stress and stress increment to be related to the finite strain, E_{IJ} , and finite strain increment, ΔE_{IJ} as

$$\tilde{T}_{IJ} = c_{IJMN} E_{MN} \text{ and } \Delta \tilde{T}_{IJ} = c_{IJMN} \Delta E_{MN}, \quad (8)$$

where c_{IJKL} are the elastic stiffness constants for the material. Using equation 8 in equation 7 and neglecting terms of $O\left(\frac{\partial u_I}{\partial X_J}\right)^3$ and higher leads to the incremental finite element equation

$$\Delta f_k^p = \left(K_{KL}^{(0)pr} + K_{KL}^{(1)pr} \right) \Delta \bar{u}_L^r, \quad (9)$$

where

$$K_{KL}^{(0)pr} = c_{KJML} \int_{V_0} \frac{\partial N^r}{\partial X_M} \frac{\partial NP}{\partial X_J} dV_0 \quad (10)$$

represents the normal linear stiffness matrix, and

$$K_{KL}^{(1)pr} = (c_{LMNJ} \delta_{KA} + c_{AJMN} \delta_{KL} + c_{MNKJ} \delta_{AL}) \times \int_{V_0} \frac{\partial N^r}{\partial X_M} \frac{\partial N^s}{\partial X_N} \frac{\partial NP}{\partial X_J} dV_0 \bar{u}_A^s \quad (11)$$

represents the incremental stiffness matrix, which is a linear function of the total displacement at a given stage of the deformation process.

The incremental force vector, Δf_k^p , for a general traction loading $\tau_{ij} n_j$ on the deformed surface, $n_i dS$, referred to the reference configuration, is obtained as

$$\Delta f_k^p = \int_{S_0} \Delta \tau_{ij} J \frac{\partial X_L}{\partial x_j} N_L \delta_{Ki} dS_0 + \int_{S_0} \tau_{ij} J \left(\frac{\partial X_L}{\partial x_j} \frac{\partial X_M}{\partial x_n} - \frac{\partial X_L}{\partial x_n} \frac{\partial X_M}{\partial x_j} \right) \frac{\partial N^r}{\partial X_M} N_L \delta_{Ki} dS_0 \delta_{nL} \Delta \bar{u}_L^r \quad (12)$$

The first term in equation 12 is the load increment due to an increment of traction, $\Delta \tau_{ij} n_j$, on the deformed surface and second term is the load increment due to the geometrical effect of the displacement increment on the total traction $\tau_{ij} n_j$ on the deformed surface at a given stage in the deformation process. Equation 12 is written in symbolic form as

$$\Delta f_k^p = \Delta F_k^p + Q_{KL}^{pr} \Delta \bar{u}_L^r, \quad (13)$$

where ΔF_k^p is the simple increment of load and Q_{KL}^{pr} is defined as the geometrical stiffness matrix. With this, the final form of the incremental finite element equations can be written as

$$\Delta f_k^p = \left(K_{KL}^{(0)pr} + K_{KL}^{(1)pr} - Q_{KL}^{pr} \right) \Delta \bar{u}_L^r. \quad (14)$$

When the structure under consideration is very slender and flexible, the small strain large deflection assumption is appropriately made. Under these circumstances, the deformation of the material is approximated by a finite rigid rotation followed by an infinitesimal strain. This approximation is obtained by the following substitutions:

$$J \approx 1 \quad V_0 \approx V \quad S_0 \approx S \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{\partial X_L}{\partial x_k} \approx \frac{\partial x_l}{\partial X_K} = \delta_{LK} + \frac{\partial N^p}{\partial X_K} \bar{u}_L^p \quad (16)$$

Equations 15 and 16 can be used to greatly simplify the construction of ΔF_k^p and Q_{KL}^{pr} .

Electrostatic Solutions

The general equations of electrostatics are given as:

$$\phi_{,ii} = -\rho \quad E_i = -\phi_{,i} \quad D_i = \epsilon_{ij} E_j \quad D_{i,i} = \rho \quad (17)$$

where ϕ is the electric potential, ρ is the volumetric charge density, E_i is the electric field, D_i is the electric displacement, and ϵ_{ij} represents the dielectric permittivity tensor for the material. In the present development, the material is assumed to be isotropic or cubic, in which case $\epsilon_{ij} = \epsilon \delta_{ij}$. Along with these differential equations, the following boundary conditions are specified on the bounding surface:

$$\phi = \bar{\phi} \quad D_i n_i = \bar{\sigma} \quad \text{on } S. \quad (18)$$

The development of the boundary integral equations begins by considering two solutions satisfying equation 17

$$(\rho, \sigma, \phi) \quad \text{and} \quad (\rho^*, \sigma^*, \phi^*) . \quad (19)$$

Let

$$\phi^* = G(x, \xi) e^*(\xi) \quad \sigma^* = F(x, \xi) e^*(\xi) , \quad (20)$$

$$\text{and } \rho^* = \delta(x - \xi) e^*(\xi) , \quad (21)$$

where

$$G(x, \xi) = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon} \frac{1}{[(x_i - \xi_i)(x_i - \xi_i)]^{1/2}} \quad (22)$$

is the fundamental singular solution, or Green's function, for the potential $\phi(x)$ at x_i due to a unit source $e(\xi)$ at ξ_i , and

$$F(x, \xi) = -\epsilon \frac{\partial G}{\partial x_i} n_i = \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{(x_i - \xi_i) n_i}{[(x_i - \xi_i)(x_i - \xi_i)]^{3/2}} \quad (23)$$

Using equations 19 through 23 allows the following integral equation to be constructed:

$$\int F(x, \xi) e^*(\xi) \phi ds - \int \delta(x - \xi) e^*(\xi) \phi dv = . \quad (24)$$

$$\int_s^s G(x, \xi) e^*(\xi) \sigma ds - \int_v^v G(x, \xi) e^*(\xi) \rho dv$$

Simplifying equation 24 gives the potential at any point, ξ_j , not on the boundary as

$$\phi(\xi) = \int_s [F(x, \xi) \phi - G(x, \xi) \sigma] ds + \int_v G(x, \xi) \rho dv \quad (25)$$

For the case of $\rho = 0$, the potential at a point, ξ_0 , on the boundary is given as a Cauchy principle value

$$\beta \phi(\xi_0) = \int_s [F(x, \xi_0) \phi - G(x, \xi_0) \sigma] ds . \quad (26)$$

The boundary element equations are developed by interpolating the surface potential and charge by shape functions

$$\phi = N^p \phi^p \quad \sigma = N^p \sigma^p \quad (27)$$

These shape functions are chosen from the same class as those used for the finite element interpolation. This is a very important step, since doing so ensures that the boundary interpolation can be regarded as that being deduced from the volume (finite element) interpolation when the values of the 3-D shape functions are evaluated on the surface. Such an interpolation scheme gives a certain "cohesion" between the boundary element and finite element formulations which greatly simplifies the method. Using equations 26 and 27 leads to the general matrix equations

$$F^{qp} \phi^p - G^{qp} \sigma^p = 0 , \quad (28)$$

where

$$F^{qp} = \int_s F(x, \xi^q) N^p ds - \beta^{(q)} \delta^{qp} \quad \text{no sum on } q \quad (29)$$

$$\text{and } G^{qp} = \int_s G(x, \xi^q) N^p ds . \quad (30)$$

Once the matrices F^{qp} and G^{qp} are constructed for the deformed surface at a given stage in the deformation, the equations corresponding to nodes with known potentials or charges are used to construct a right hand side vector for equation 28, and the resulting square left hand side matrix is inverted and the remaining surface potentials and charges are solved for. A more detailed discussion of boundary element methods can be found in [6].

Electrostatic Force On A Body In A Non-uniform Electric Field

The electrostatic force on an arbitrary body in a non-uniform electric field is given as [2]

$$F_j = \int_v \tau_{kj, k}^E dv = \int_s \tau_{kj}^E n_k ds , \quad (31)$$

where τ_{kj}^E is the Maxwell electrostatic stress tensor

$$\tau_{kj}^E = \epsilon_0 \left[\eta^2 E_i E_j - \frac{1}{2} E_k E_k \delta_{ij} \right] , \quad (32)$$

with $\eta = (\epsilon/\epsilon_0)^{1/2}$ denoting the index of refraction of the material. Using the interpolated potentials gives

$$\tau_{ij}^E = \epsilon_0 \left[\eta^2 \frac{\partial X_M}{\partial x_i} \frac{\partial X_N}{\partial x_j} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial X_M}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial X_N}{\partial x_k} \right] \frac{\partial N^p}{\partial X_M} \frac{\partial N^q}{\partial X_N} \phi^p \phi^q \quad (33)$$

and the increment

$$\Delta \tau_{ij}^E = \epsilon_0 \left[\eta^2 \left(\frac{\partial X_M}{\partial x_i} \frac{\partial X_N}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial X_M}{\partial x_j} \frac{\partial X_N}{\partial x_i} \right) - \frac{\partial X_M}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial X_N}{\partial x_k} \right] \frac{\partial N^p}{\partial X_M} \frac{\partial N^q}{\partial X_N} \phi^p \Delta \phi^q \quad (34)$$

The simplifications allowed by the small strain large deflection approximation given by equations 15 and 16 are applied to equations 33 and 34. One important point that must be mentioned is that in order to evaluate the shape function derivatives appearing in equations 33 and 34, the potential has to be evaluated at nodes interior to the boundary. This can be achieved using equation 25 or by solving a finite element problem for the potentials. Unfortunately, space limitations do not permit these points to be fully elaborated upon.

Discussion and Conclusion

The equations derived in the previous sections are applied incrementally in a series of load steps and linear solutions. The basic procedure for a given load step is to apply an increment in the potential vector, $\Delta \phi^q$, and compute the surface tractions from equations 33 and 34. With this, the stiffness terms and force vector in equation

14 are computed and the resulting linear system is solved for the displacement increments, Δu_i^p . The total displacement and potential is updated and the process is continued.

This method has been applied to a simple model of a silicon diaphragm as shown schematically in figure 1. This structure was studied for different thicknesses and the voltage-deflection behavior is shown in figure 2. These results show that for smaller voltages, the deflection, while non-linear, behaves predictably. At larger voltages, the deflection becomes very large and there is observed an abrupt change in the voltage deflection behavior. This critical voltage is generally referred to as the pull-in voltage for the diaphragm. Figure 3 shows a comparison of the general nonlinear formulation and a linear formulation in which the load is updated as a function of the total displacement, but a simple constant stiffness is used in the solution at each step. It is seen that the two solutions agree prior to pull-in, but for higher voltages the linear stiffness method does not predict the abrupt change in deflection.

References

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Figures

Material: Silicon

Figure 1. Dimensions of a silicon diaphragm for the example problem.

Figure 2. Voltage-deflection behavior for a silicon diaphragm.

Figure 3. Comparison of linear and nonlinear solutions.